

Engagement of Teachers to Learning Action Cell: Reflection on Teaching Practices

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Abstract. This study uncovered the experiences and challenges teachers face in their engagement in learning action cells. There were ten (10) teachers of Kapalong-East District, Division of Davao del Norte, who participated in the study. This study made use of a phenomenological approach to extract the reflections of the participants. The in-depth interview was employed to gather some information with regard to their respective experiences and challenges. Based on the results of the thematic analysis of the responses from the participants of the study, the following findings revealed that their corresponding themes were revealed: the experiences of teachers in engaging the Learning Action cell probed in promoting collaboration and shared learning, increasing learners' engagement and enhancing problem-solving and innovative skills. The challenges of teachers in engaging the Learning Action Cell employed were time constraints, inadequate facilitation, and resource limitations. The educational management insights drawn from the findings of the study were the following: cultivating collaborative culture, professional development integration, and continuous improvement. Thus, Learning Action Cells transpired as a foundation for sustainable growth, connecting teachers, learners, and the broader school community in a shared commitment to educational excellence. Making this study meaningful, publication to a reputable journal was essential.

KEY WORDS

1. engagement 2. learning action cell 3. teaching practices

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1. Introduction

Outstanding teachers contribute to the development of great students. They are one aspect that impacts student accomplishment and the school's overall performance. Teachers must be knowledgeable about contemporary educational trends and issues. With these needs in mind, the development of action research bridges the gap between theory and practice by grounding educational decisions in real-world experiences. Educators can make evidence-based decisions by collecting and analyzing data, leading to more effective teaching strategies and improved learning outcomes—personalizing professional development. Teachers require more training to get new skills and information to tackle new problems and reform in the classroom. SLAC can assist teachers in becoming more professional to help the organization meet its goals. A training program like SLAC in a school provides people with the necessary skills and information or attitude to carry out their responsibilities. Training is concerned with broadening an

individual's skills in preparation for future duties, whereas development is concerned with an organization's efforts to enable learning among its personnel (George Scott, 2012). As a result, addressing these challenges and satisfying the school's needs requires a training program. It also serves as a bridge between novice and experienced instructors, assisting them in overcoming the challenges of guiding students to greater levels of learning and self-development. Teachers require professional development programs such as SLAC, which should not be done without reform. Teachers can be more methodical and logical in teaching using the School Learning Action Cell (Kazmi et.al., 2011). Teachers must be prepared to tackle new challenges and tasks to fully fulfill their classroom responsibilities, given the teacher's complex function in modern schools (Zuljan Vogrinc, 2011). Various developments are improving and altering the educational landscape today. The School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) is the venue for in-service training and teacher development that is both ongoing and cost-effective. To this end, The Department of Education fully supports its teachers' ongoing professional development, which is based on the principle of lifelong learning and recognition of teaching as a profession in which teachers must possess expert knowledge and specialized abilities, which they must acquire and maintain through continuous study (UNESCO, 2006). Moreover, this advocacy of DepEd implies that every teacher should be properly guided and equipped with the know-how of the teaching learning processes through revisiting or reviewing some areas or concerned in performing the duties and responsibilities of an effective and efficient teacher. Successful teaching is a result of the systematic use of appropriate strategies for delivering and assessing the learning objectives targeted for the lesson. In New York, it was pointed out that school principals act as catalysts for change. A principal needs to be a visionary who uses his or

her formal leadership strategically. One must be knowledgeable, thoughtful, insightful, and reflective in dealing with all the facets of leadership, as it is a necessary ingredient for leading others, implementing and actualizing the school vision, and having sound decision-making skills. Furthermore, as a school leader, one is expected to highlight leadership skills that are far more reaching and worthy of emulating, particularly among the people under his or her care. One must be systematic enough to look at how the teachers develop their skills based on what the principal provides them, specifically in the technical assistance area, which is the core of being a leader (Tomal, 2013). In the Philippines, it reiterates that if the group (LAC) facilitator consistently undertakes the abovementioned functions, the members eventually learn and exhibit these skills. Work engagement, on the other hand, is also worthy of consideration as individuals who are highly engaged in their jobs and are motivated by the work itself tend to work harder and more productively than others and are more likely to produce the results their customers, who are the learners want and is expecting to do, as well as the organization to where they belong. Education has become the primary mechanism providing individuals with the knowledge, skills and competencies needed by the society of the day. However, educational provision typically lags behind the emergence of need (Ortigas, 2015). In the Philippine setting, DO 35, s. 2016, institutionalized the Learning Action Cell (LAC) to improve teachers' competence. It is an avenue of collaboration and sharing of best practices among teachers towards improving students' learning. Accordingly, the Davao Region directed all school division offices and schools to institutionalize the LAC sessions to support the ongoing professional growth of its teaching personnel (Regional Memo 094 s. 2017). Subsequently, Davao City enjoined all the school heads to take the lead in organizing the LAC and to ensure that the holding of regu-

lar LAC sessions is established, maintained, and sustained. It also directed school heads to monitor LAC activities and evaluate their impact on school improvement (Division et al. 1993 s. 2018). To solve these issues, it's critical to establish a supportive environment, provide ample time and resources, provide training in facilitation techniques, and promote a culture of cooperation and ongoing improvement inside the school or educational institution. Fostering a supportive environment, allocating resources, training, and fostering cooperation was essential for addressing school issues and promoting problem-solving, collaboration, and community development. Thus, this study finds meaning and significance.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The primary purpose of this study was phenomenological inquiry, which explored the experiences of the public elementary teachers in Learning Action Cells. This study aimed to investigate the impact of the Learning Actions Cells on public elementary teachers. Specifically, this study explored how exposure to Action Learning Cells affects public elementary teachers teaching practices and professional development. This included how public elementary teachers interact during Learning Action Cell Sessions that influence the professional development experiences, including the impact of teaching practices, attitudes, and skills—and lastly, the implications of these findings for promoting the professional development of public elementary teachers. At its inception, this research also considered exploring the experiences of public elementary teachers engaged in Learning Action Cells sessions to enhance overall teaching practices and help readers achieve their professional development. In the in-depth interview sessions, important details on the challenges that restrain public elementary teachers from engaging with Learning Action Cells were unveiled. Moreover, this study aspired to develop insights from the findings of the information data gathered. The insights drawn from this study are useful contribution propositions for the reasonable and logical implementation of exposures in the public elementary teachers engaging in Learning Action Cells. Further, this study enriched the effort to obtain information and help public elementary teachers engage Learning Action Cells for easy, relevant, and successful professional development.

1.2. Research Questions—The study was anchored to explore the lived experiences of teachers' engagement in learning action cells, including the challenges that they encounter; this study sought answers to the following research questions:

- (1) What are teachers' experiences in engaging the Learning Action Cell?
- (2) What are teachers' challenges in engaging in the Learning Action Cell?
- (3) What educational management insights can be drawn from the findings of the study?

1.3. Definition of Terms—To fully understand the terms used in this study, they were defined operationally: Learning Action Cell. It is a group of teachers who engage in collaborative learning sessions to solve shared challenges encountered in the school facilitated by the school head or a designated leader. Teaching Practices. This was a form of work-integrated learning described as a period of time when students worked in the relevant industry to receive specific in-service training and apply theory in practice.

1.4. Significant of the Study—The results of this study are significant to the following: Department of Education. Learning action cells could be of great importance to the De-

partment of Education. They could be vital in promoting collaboration, professional development, data-driven decision-making, continuous improvement, and innovation within the Department of Education. By leveraging educators' collective expertise and experiences, these cells enhance teaching and learning practices and ultimately benefit students and the education system. School administrators. Learning action cells offer school administrators a structured and collaborative approach to professional development, reflective practice, problem-solving, collaboration, and data-informed decision-making. Administrators can enhance their leadership effectiveness and contribute to school improvement efforts by engaging in these processes. Teachers. Learning action cells were vital for teachers as they promoted professional develop-

ment, reflective practice, peer learning and support, action-oriented approaches, data-driven decision-making, and continuous improvement. By actively participating in learning action cells, teachers could enhance their teaching practices, improve student learning outcomes, and contribute to a vibrant professional learning community. Pupils. Learning action cells are an important aspect of education for pupils as they provide numerous benefits and contribute to their overall development. They provide a dynamic and engaging learning environment that nurtures pupils' intellectual, social, and emotional development. By actively participating in action cells, pupils acquire essential skills, knowledge, and attitudes that prepare them for future challenges and enable them to become lifelong learners.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This study is anchored on one prominent scholar in the field of social learning theory in social work is (1961-1963), Albert Bandura, a Canadian-American psychologist who was the David Starr Jordan Professor Emeritus of Social Science in Psychology at Stanford University., often referred to as the "Social Learning Theory" Social learning theory suggests that social behavior is learned by observing and imitating the behavior of others. Psychologist Albert Bandura developed the social learning theory as an alternative to fellow psychologist B.F's earlier work. Skinner is known for his influence on behaviorism. While behavioral psychology focuses on how the environment and reinforcement affect behavior, Bandura said individuals can learn behavior through observation. Social work theory refers to a collection of ideas, concepts, and frameworks that guide social workers in understanding and addressing social issues and helping individuals, families, groups, and communities. These theories provide a foundation

for social work practice and inform the interventions and strategies social workers use to promote social change and improve well-being. Social workers may draw on multiple theories and frameworks depending on the needs of their clients and the specific context in which they work. Social work theory is a set of ideas, concepts, and frameworks that guide social workers in understanding and addressing social issues. It provides a foundation for social work practice and informs interventions and strategies to promote social change and improve well-being. Some prominent social work theories include Systems Theory, Strengths-Based Perspective, Ecological Perspective, Person-Centered Theory, Cognitive-Behavioral Theory, and Empowerment Theory. These theories focus on understanding relationships, interactions, and dynamics within families, communities, and societal structures. Social workers may draw on multiple theories and frameworks depending on their clients' needs and the context in which they work.

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

2. Methodology

This chapter presents the method, research participants, data collection, role of the researcher, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations. The explored facts and knowledge in this study necessitate the consequent design and implementation, as elaborated in this chapter.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption was a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret the data collected in a specific field of study. It establishes the background used for the following conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and were elaborated. Ontology. This part of the research pertains to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. Creswell (2012) states that reality is subjective and multiple, as seen by the study participants. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. Reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the researcher relied on the voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes and themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The participant’s answers to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct the commonality and discreteness of responses. The researcher ensured that the participants’ responses were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result.

The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded from making personal bias as the study progressed. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln, as cited by Creswell (2012), state that, on the epistemological assumption, the researcher would attempt to lessen the distance between themselves and the participants. It is suggested that, as a researcher, time is expected to be spent in the field with participants, and the researcher becomes an 'insider'. It was assumed that the researcher established a close interaction with the participants to gain direct information that shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry. Axiology refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2012) states that the role of values in a study was significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discuss values that shape the narrative and include their interpretation in conjunction with the interpretation of participants. The researcher upheld the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understood the personal and value-laden nature of the information gathered from the study. The researcher preserved the merit of the participants' answers and carefully understood the answers in the light of the participants' interpretation. Rhetoric meant reporting what reality

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—This study used a phenomenological approach and qualitative methodology. The researcher conducted the interview using an interview guide, which the participants answered based on their experiences and practices related to this study. An in-depth interview was a qualitative research technique involving intensive individual interviews with a few respondents to explore their perspectives on a particular idea, program, or

was through the eyes of my research participants. The researcher used personal voice and qualitative terms such as credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability instead of internal and external validity and objectivity. As Patton (2000) defined phenomenology as an inquiry that asks, "What is the structure and essence of the experience of his phenomenon for these people?" The goal of this research study would work well with this definition in trying to understand the teachers' experiences on the equitability of a technology-integrated environment. Guba (2007) pointed out that the researcher needs to prepare for an investigation greater in depth and breadth than the offered description implied. He suggested that the information be viewed as "the tip of the iceberg." The researcher implemented the qualitative research method of phenomenology to allow for the exploration of the teachers' experiences, particularly on attending the Learning Action Cell. Burns and Grove (2003) stated that phenomenology was a philosophy, an approach or perspective to living, learning and doing research". The goal of phenomenological research was to capture lived experiences, find meaning that may or may not be known to the person who experienced them, and describe the phenomenon through a composite narrative. For the qualitative researcher, the only reality was the reality of the participants involved in the research situations constructed.

situation (Boyce Neale, 2006). Interviews are primarily done in qualitative research and occur when researchers ask one or more participants general, open-ended questions and record their answers. A phenomenological approach was used to gain a broader insight. Phenomenology was described as an approach to qualitative research focusing on the commonality of a lived experience within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach was to arrive at a

description of the nature of the particular phenomenon for investigatory inquiry. (Creswell, 2013).

2.3. Design and Procedure—The study utilized a qualitative research method employing a phenomenological qualitative design. According to Lester, phenomenological research was concerned with studying experiences from the individual's perspective, "bracketing" taken-for-granted assumptions and usual ways of perceiving. The phenomenological approach is based on a paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity. It emphasized the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. Thus, it was powerful for understanding subjective experiences, gaining insights into participants' motivations and actions, and cutting through the clutter of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. Qualitative research was mostly associated with words, language, and experiences rather than measurements, statistics, and numerical figures. It refers to the inductive, holistic, epic, subjective, and process-oriented methods used to understand, interpret, describe, and develop a theory on phenomena or settings. It was a systematic, subjective approach to describing life experiences and giving them meaning (Burns Grove 2003). The phenomenological research design was selected in this study to collect data on the experiences and challenges of public elementary teachers who were engaged in Learning Action Cells. This research approach deepened the understanding of nature and the meaning of everyday experiences. According to Corbetta (2003), the phenomenological research design was a qualitative type of research for which interviews provide an in-depth method that can grant access to deep knowledge and explanations and help to grasp the subject's perspective. Bryman (2012) posited that personal and detailed stories could be told through interviews or face-to-face discussions, focusing on how the interviewee

understands and explains different phenomena. The researcher aimed to draw an in-depth study on the experiences and challenges of teachers in learning action cells. Qualitative research was interested in understanding how people interpret their experiences, how they construct their worlds, and what meaning they attribute to their experiences" (Merriam, 2009). This form of research provided a deep understanding of the subject and results in enhanced explanatory power. The researcher becomes "a part of the world they study; the knower and the known are taken to be inseparable" (Hatch, 2002). Because of the researcher's involvement, however, "much qualitative research is subjective" (Wrench, Thomas-Maddox, Richmond, and McCroskey, 2008). Bloomberg and Volpe (2008) described qualitative research as "idea generation." Its design was proposed up front, but it is open and emergent rather than rigid and fixed to permit exploration. It uses small samples purposefully. It takes place within natural contexts, and real-world situations are studied as they unfold. Its framework allows for flexibility and creativity. The qualitative research explored and described teachers' experiences and challenges in engaging in learning action cells. The research technique used was a modified van Kaam method described by Moustakas (2000) based on recorded and transcribed interviews using semi-structured questions to capture the teachers' experiences and challenges in engaging with Learning Action Cells. Specifically, phenomenology was the study of the subjective experiences of others. It researched the world through another person's eyes by discovering how they interpret their experiences. It describes the meaning of the lived experiences of several individuals about a concept or a phenomenon. Phenomenology explores the struc-

tures of consciousness in human experiences, as Polkinghorne (2000) noted. This involved procedures which the qualitative researchers should follow. First, the researcher wrote research questions that would explore the meaning of life experiences for individuals and asked individuals to describe these experiences. The researcher collected data from individuals who had experienced the phenomenon under investigation, typically via lengthy interviews. Next, the data analysis involved horizontalization, which extracted significant statements from transcribed interviews. The significant statements were transformed into clusters of meanings according to how each would fall under specific psychological and phenomenological concepts. Moreover, these transformations were tied up together to make a general description of the experience – both the textual description of what was experienced and the structural description of how it was experienced. The researcher incorporated the meaning of the experience here. Finally, the report was written so that readers better understand the essential, invariant structure of the experience’s essence. Conversely, several challenges have been pointed out. The researcher required a solid grounding in the philosophical guidelines of phenomenology. The subjects selected in the study were individuals who had experienced the phenomenon. The researcher needed to bracket their own experiences and observations, which was difficult. The researcher also needed to decide how and when their observations were incorporated into the study. Accordingly, Hycner’s (2008) phenomenology in business research studies ideas were generated from abundant data using induction, human interests, and stakeholder perspec-

tives, which may have reflected on the study. Advantages associated with phenomenology include a better understanding of meanings attached by people and its contribution to developing new theories. Its disadvantages include difficulties with analysis and interpretation, usually lower levels of validity and reliability compared to positivism, and more time and other resources required for data collection (Hycner, 2008). Similarly, Schutz (2010) stressed that the purpose of the phenomenological approach is to illuminate the specific and identify phenomena through how the actors perceive them in a situation. In the human sphere, this translates typically into gathering ‘deep’ information and perceptions through inductive, qualitative methods such as interviews, discussions, and participant observation and representing it from the perspective of the research participant(s). Phenomenology is concerned with the study of experience from the individual’s perspective, ‘bracketing’ taken-for-granted assumptions, and usual ways of perceiving. Epistemologically, phenomenological approaches were based on the paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity and emphasized the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. As such, they were dominant in understanding the subjective experience, gaining insights into people’s motivations and actions, and cutting through the clutter of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. The researcher’s purpose was to employ the phenomenology type of qualitative method research since the focal point of this study is to investigate and explore the public elementary teacher’s experiences in engaging with learning action cells.

2.4. Research Participants—The key informants of this study were the selected public elementary grade teachers of Kapalong-East District District, Division of Davao Davao Del

Norte. The researcher utilized ten (10) teachers for qualitative participants in an in-depth interview (IDI) who were purposely selected. The informants should have been teaching three

or more years in the service and got a rating of Very Satisfactory in his/her performance for three consecutive years. The researcher utilized the purposive sampling design since the participants were chosen based on the criteria or

purpose of the study. It was also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings was authentic (Marshall, 1996).

2.5. *Ethical Considerations*—Ethical considerations were of paramount importance in the design of this research study. The researcher needed to consider several ethical issues about the research participant groups addressed in this fieldwork. Ethical considerations were specified as one of the most critical parts of the research. The researcher adhered to promoting the aims of the research, imparting factual knowledge, truth, and prevention of error. Social Value. Research was essential to society. This study focused on the experiences and challenges of teachers engaging with learning action cells. Thus, the social problem that pushed the researcher's interest was the challenges the teacher encountered in engaging with learning action cells. This study could serve as a basis for higher authorities to create more programs and resolutions where learners could benefit. Informed Consent. Gaining the trust and support of research participants is critical to informed and ethical academic inquiry and phenomenological research (Walker, 2007 as cited by Pellerin, 2012). All participants were given an informed consent form before scheduling the interviews and participating in the phenomenological research process. Each participant was required to provide a signed personal acknowledgment, consent, and an indication of a willingness to participate in the study release. The purpose of the informed consent letter was to introduce the research effort, provide contact information, articulate the study's intent, request voluntary participation by the recipients, and identify the anticipated information that the informants were expected to provide. All participants were then required to sign and return the

consent letter to the researcher before participating. In the conduct and practice of this study, the Treaty Principle of Participation, as cited by McLeod (2009), was adhered to. The invitation to participate ensured that participation in the research was entirely voluntary and based on understanding adequate information. The recruitment and selection of participants were lodged in the appendices of this study. The Vulnerability of Research Participants. The participants of this study were deemed capable of answering the research instrument, for they served as the first-hand source of information. Thus, the researcher then assured the participants that they could easily be reached through their contact number and address if there were clarifications or questions about the study. Risks, Benefits, and Safety. The recruitment of the respondents was free of coercion, undue influence, or inducement. Moreover, respondents were provided with the contact numbers of the panel chair or panel members in case they had queries related to the study. This was done to answer the respondents' possible questions. Furthermore, if respondents experienced possible discomfort and inconvenience while answering the questions, they were not compelled to participate in any manner. Further, the researcher had to ensure that the respondents were safe during the survey and interview. Thus, the questionnaire was distributed in a safe venue and administered at a convenient time. The dominant concern of this study was the Treaty Principle of Protection, as reflected in the respect for the rights of privacy and confidentiality and the minimization of risk. This was done by assigning pseudonyms for each informant so as not to dis-

close their identity. The possibility of a degree of risk inherent to this was minimized by taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2002 to ensure that the data could not be traced back to their real sources to protect participants' identities. Thus, utmost care was taken to ensure the anonymity of the data sources. Hence, any printed outputs from this study were kept anonymous. Furthermore, all the issues were given consideration so that there was no conflict of interest among the researcher and the respondents. Any misleading information and representation of primary data findings in a biased way were avoided. Justice. The respondents were informed of the researcher's role and their corresponding role during data gathering. They were then briefed that they had to be fully honest in answering the survey questions and that any type of communication about the research was done with honesty. Similarly, they were informed that they were the ones to benefit first from the study's results. Transparency. The results of the study could then be accessed by the respondents and heads of the participating schools because the information was available and placed on CDs or other storage devices, which could be requested from the researcher. Also, by learning about the study's results, classroom teachers would be aware of the significance of the study and its contribution to their well-being. Further, each participant was advised that they had the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process and that they could request to be allowed to verify their transcript after the interview. The participants were allowed to amend or remove any information they felt might identify them. The researcher reserved the right to employ pseudonyms and change names or non-significant dates to protect the participant's identity in all subsequent data analysis and reporting. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured the possession of the needed qualifications to conduct the study. The researcher had completed the academic requirements and passed the comprehensive examination before thesis writing, which was the last requirement to obtain the researcher's master's degree. They were qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. Also, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the study would reach its completion. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher strived to complete the study successfully within the specified time, and they were equipped with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee would help enhance the paper by giving the needed suggestions and recommendations. The researcher also had to ensure they had enough funds to continue and finish the research. Community Involvement. The researcher showed respect for the local traditions, culture, and views of the respondents in this study. Moreover, this study would not involve any use of deceit in any stage of its implementation, specifically in the recruitment of the participants or methods of data collection. Furthermore, the researcher deemed it necessary to express their great pleasure for their wholehearted participation in this study. Plagiarism and Fabrication as the researcher. The researcher respected other works by adequately citing the author and rewriting what someone else had said in their own way. He also understood the context of the study. He avoided copying-pasting the text verbatim from the reference paper and using quotes to indicate that the text had been taken from another paper. Similarly, they would assure them of honesty in working on the manuscript and that there was no intentional misrepresentation in the study and making up of data and results or purposefully putting forward conclusions that were not accurate.

2.6. *Role of the Researcher*—The researcher wrote a letter asking permission to the Schools Division Superintendent. After this, another letter of permission was secured and submitted to the participants. Upon approval, I used the forms of data collection prescribed in the qualitative design. In this study, an in-depth interview was recorded. It was important for the researcher to get the subjective interaction between the study participants. The researcher relied heavily on naturalistic methods (interviewing and audio-recording), using the interpretivist paradigm. Interpretive approaches relied heavily on naturalistic methods like interviewing, observation, and analysis of existing texts. These methods ensured an adequate dialog between the researchers and those with whom they interacted to construct a meaningful

2.7. *Data Collection*—The following was the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study in the identified school during the third week of August 2023. The researcher sent a letter addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent with Chapters 1 and 2 attached, together with the research instrument, which explained the study's objectives and the participants' identification. The researcher waited for the SDS's response before conducting it. Asking permission from the school heads. After securing the approval of the SDS, the researcher sent letters to the principals of the schools during the first week of September 2023 explaining the study to be conducted in their schools. Obtaining consent from the participants. The researcher asked permission from the participants during the first week of September 2023. They were formally oriented about the study and the process they would un-

reality collaboratively. Yin, as cited by Aquilam (2014), suggested numerous forms of data collection, including documents, archival records, interviews, direct observation, participant observation, and physical artifacts. In order to have legitimate and trustworthy data on teachers' pedagogical innovations, the researcher conducted an in-depth interview and focus group discussion. This interview explored the experiences and challenges of public elementary teachers engaging in Learning Action Cells. The participants were encouraged to express their answers most comfortably. The interview with the teacher was transcribed word for word. Lastly, the researcher analyzed the data collected using discourse analysis and thematic analysis. Creswell (2007) suggested that to succeed in the study, the data must be stored to be easily found and protected from damage and loss.

dergo as participants. Conducting the interview. The researcher conducted the in-depth interview using the interview questionnaire during the second and third weeks of September 2023. The profile of the participants was taken, notes were jotted down, and conversations were recorded using a sound recorder for ease of transcription. The researcher carefully listened and responded actively during the interviews. Transcribing the responses of the interviewees. The researcher transcribed the responses of the interviewees precisely by recalling their answers from the sound recorder on the fourth week of September 2023 Data Coding and thematizing. After the transcription, the data were categorized and coded in October 2023. Then, themes were extracted, and individual participant data were compared and contrasted. The researcher then conducted a second round of interviews (FGD) to corroborate any data that needed further explanation and input from the participants; additional information gathered was examined thoroughly and integrated into the existing body

of data. After this, data were compared and contrasted between the participants in order to

2.8. Data Analysis—In this study, thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the gathered data. The researcher analyzed the answers of the participants from the conducted interviews using Creswell’s Model, specifically the identifying of themes approach. According to Creswell (2012), themes in qualitative research are similar codes aggregated together to form a major idea in the database. Familiarization with the data is common to all forms of qualitative analysis. The researcher immersed herself in and became intimately familiar with their data, reading and re-reading it and noting any initial analytic observations. Coding was also a common element of many approaches to qualitative analysis. It involves generating pithy labels for important features of the data relevant to the (broad) research question guiding the analysis. Coding is not simply a data reduction method; it is also an analytic process, so codes capture both a semantic and conceptual reading of the

2.9. Framework of Analysis—This study employed a qualitative research method. Rigorous and systematic steps were observed in analyzing the information gathered from the teacher-participants. Data were analyzed following the steps outlined by O’Connor and Gibson (2003) on qualitative data analysis: Organizing the Data. The data were organized in a way that was easy to look at, allowing the researcher to go through each topic to pick out concepts and themes. Finding and Organizing Ideas and Concepts. Look for specific words or ideas that keep coming up, then organize these ideas into codes or categories. Building Over-Archiving Themes in the Data. Each response category

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—

come up with patterns and trends.

The researcher will code every data item and end this phase by collating all their codes and relevant data extracts. Searching for themes was a coherent and meaningful pattern in the data relevant to the research question. The researcher would end this phase by collating all the coded data relevant to each theme. Reviewing themes. The researcher reflected on whether the themes tell a convincing and compelling story about the data and began to define the nature of each individual theme and the relationship between the themes. Defining and naming themes: The researcher prepared a detailed analysis of each theme, identifying the ‘essence’ of each theme and constructing a concise, punchy, and informative name for each theme. Writing up involves weaving together the analytic narrative and data extracts to tell the reader a coherent and persuasive story about the data and contextualizing it in relation to existing literature.

had one or more associated themes that gave a deeper meaning to the data. Different categories could be collapsed under one main over-arching theme. Ensuring Reliability and Validity in the Data Analysis and the Findings. Findings were more dependable when they could be confirmed from several independent sources. Their validity was enhanced when they were confirmed by more than one “instrument” measuring the same thing. The researcher also completed the two other steps in this study: writing, which was drafting the output of the data analysis by weaving stories from narratives and literature and presenting them, and thematic and comprehensive presentation of the output in artistic graphs and illustrations.

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

The concepts of validity and reliability would be relatively foreign to the field of qualitative research. Qualitative researchers substitute data trustworthiness instead of focusing on reliability and validity. Trustworthiness consists of the components such as credibility, transferability, dependability and conformability (Harts, 2016). Credibility refers to the extent to which a research account is believable and appropriate, particularly regarding the level of agreement between participants and the researcher. Credibility is most often associated with the framework Yvonna Lincoln and Egon Guba presented. Transferability was defined as the degree to which the results of qualitative research can be transferred to other contexts or settings with other respondents. The researcher facilitated the transferability judgment by a potential user through thick description. Dependability was the extent to which other researchers could repeat the study and ensure that the findings were consistent. In other words, if a person wanted to replicate your study, they should have enough information from your research report to do so and obtain similar findings as your study did. Conformability refers to the objectivity of research during data collection and data analysis. There needs to be congruency between two or more independent persons about the data's accuracy, relevance, or meaning (Polit and Beck, 2012). Conformability also indicates a means to demonstrate quality.

3. Results and Discussion

This part of the study dealt with the research questions and their answers based on the responses of the participants. The participants unfolded their experiences and challenges as they engaged with the Learning Action Cell.

3.1. Experiences of Teachers in Engaging to Learning Action Cell—The collaborative nature of LACs provides the best avenue for teachers to share their insights, challenges, and teaching practices with colleagues. This engagement promotes a sense of community and professional support, allowing teachers to reflect on their methods and explore innovative approaches to enhance student learning. Also, through LACs, teachers were aware of the opportunity to actively participate in shaping their professional development, modifying it to their specific needs and interests. Through this shared journey of reflection, collaboration, and actionable strategies, teachers refine their instructional techniques and cultivate a deeper understanding of their role in the broader educational community. The experiences within LACs contribute to a culture of continuous learning and improvement, positively impacting both individual teaching practices and the overall quality of education within the school.

3.1.1. They were promoting Collaboration and Shared Learning—Teachers through Learning Action Cells often experience opportunities to collaborate with colleagues, share their best practices, and learn from each other, which leads to their improved teaching methods, content knowledge, and overall professional development. Thus, it develops a culture of continuous improvement. The study's findings agree with the findings of Jhimson (2019), which indicate that the conducted LAC sessions contribute much to teachers' professional growth and development. Likewise, the study's findings are also supported by the study of Ryan (2019), which has proven that LACs effectively engage a group of teachers in collaborating and solving shared challenges. Also, LAC sessions encourage critical reflection amongst

teachers, which increases their understanding and knowledge of the curriculum and classroom practices. The participants shared that through LAC sessions, they were able to share and learn best practices and gained support among colleagues. They were also given the opportunity to improve their teaching practices through feedback mechanisms and provision

3.1.2. Increasing Learners' Engagement—As teachers implement new strategies learned from the learning action cells discussions, they observed increased student engagement in the classroom, which motivated them to increase creativity and share resources that will benefit fellow teacher participants of the LAC. Implementing Learning Action Cells (LACs) has demonstrated a fascinating outcome in increased learners' engagement within educational settings. Learning Action Cells create a constructive flow of outcomes, empowering teachers, nurturing a supportive learning environment, and ultimately leading to increased learner engagement. They turn classrooms into vibrant hubs of active learning and academic growth (Huang, 2007). It can be gleaned from the responses of the participants that they were able to maximize learners' participation and engagement by employing new strategies. This is supported by Participants 6 and 10 who also shared that learners' participation were heightened and total performance was improved. The foregoing results of the study were consistent

3.1.3. Enhancing Problem Solving and Innovative Skills—Learning Action Cells provide a plan of action for teachers to identify specific teaching-related problems and find possible solutions through the development of innovative practices that lead to the improvement of their teaching-learning approaches. Research evidence shows collaboration and cooperation of teachers allow them to identify common problems/issues that they face in the classroom, such

of teaching resources. These findings were consistent with the results of the study of Ospina and Sanchez (2010), which specified that LAC sessions formed teacher study groups that were commonly sustained by committed teachers who share similar interests and reach individual goals through interaction and collaboration with other colleagues.

with the findings made by Ryan (2019) that as teachers actively participate in collaborative professional development through LACs, they gain insights into innovative and effective teaching strategies, and the application of these strategies in the classroom not only enriches the learning environment but also captivates the interest of learners. Moreover, the collaborative discussions and constructive feedback within LACs contribute to a more dynamic and responsive approach to teaching, fostering an environment where learners feel actively involved in their own learning (Jhimson, 2019). The study findings were also supported by Eksi (2010), who stated that the increased engagement of learners becomes a noticeable and positive outcome, creating a progressive effect that enhances the overall educational experience and contributes to improved academic achievements. The success of LACs in boosting learners' engagement stresses the effectiveness of collaborative professional development in positively shaping classroom dynamics and student learning outcomes (Jhimson, 2019).

as low engagement of learners, difficulty with specific concepts, and inadequate resources that must be a common ground for brainstorming solutions with innovative strategies therein (Hismanoğlu, 2010). On the other hand, the findings of the study were affirmed by the study of Showers and Joyce (1996) which emphasized that those teachers who had a coaching relationship and shared aspects of teaching, planned together, and pooled their experiences, were

Fig. 3. Emerging themes on teachers' engagement to Learning Action Cell

able to practice new skills and strategies more frequently and applied them more appropriately. Similarly, Eksi (2010), highlighted the notion that a successful facilitation of problem solving and innovative skills development of teachers in the institution through learning action cells will improve their effectiveness as educators. The above responses explained how LAC sessions help teachers deal with existing problems in their respective classrooms through shared innovation and techniques. Participants expressed that they were able to reflect on their shared classroom experiences and successful approaches so they could focus and address struggles encountered. Moreover, the participants emphasized that through LAC, sharing experiences helped them improve their teaching approaches and build rapport with other teachers. These findings were consistent with the results of the study of Sun et al. (2020), which indicated that sharing strategies and resources in

Learning Action Cells leads to innovative practices like leveled lesson plans, individualized learning activities, and technology-supported differentiation. Further, the results were consistent with Gurnani and Ramani's (2016) major findings that Learning Action Cells provide valuable insights and suggestions for tackling teaching challenges. Acknowledging the importance of Learning Action Cells, effectively integrating technology, sharing experiences, and exploring new tools to innovate modern information, communications, and technology for instruction, assessment, and student engagement practices (Jhimson, 2019). Figure 3 shows teachers' Experiences Engaging with the Learning Action Cell and the emergence of the three themes: Promoting Collaboration and Shared Learning, Demands, Increasing Learners' Engagement, and Enhancing Problem-Solving and Innovation Skills.

3.2. Challenges of Teachers in Engaging to Learning Action Cell—Teachers face various challenges when engaging in Learning Ac-

tion Cells (LACs). Though they offer invaluable opportunities, they are not without their challenges. Balancing heavy workloads with

dedicated LAC time can be difficult, creating scheduling conflicts and hindering regular participation. Even when present, ineffective facilitation can lead to unfocused discussions and a feeling of wasted time. Furthermore, unclear expectations around roles and responsibilities can cause confusion and discourage some teachers from actively contributing (Ryan, 2019). Additionally, according to Jhimson (2019), limited resources and lack of administrative support can create logistical hurdles and dampen mo-

3.2.1. Time Constraints—Time constraints emerge as a major barrier for teachers' participation in Learning Action Cells (LACs). Juggling heavy workloads with dedicated LAC meetings feels like a constant tug-of-war. Scheduling conflicts between teachers, school activities, and personal commitments often untangle attempts at consistent participation. The responses above revealed that participants had a hard time balancing their responsibilities. They shared that it was a challenge for them to cope with the demands of their work, especially in conducting LAC sessions. The present findings of the study were consistent with the result findings of Ryan

3.2.2. Inadequate Facilitation—Inadequate facilitation stands out as one of the significant challenges faced by teachers engaging in Learning Action Cells (LACs), hindering the effectiveness of collaborative professional development. Facilitation plays a crucial role in guiding discussions, maintaining focus, and ensuring that the goals of the LAC are met. Thus, when facilitation is insufficient, discussions may lack direction, and participants may struggle to stay engaged in the activity. Teachers find it challenging to translate insights from discussions into actionable steps without proper guidance. Accordingly, inadequate facilitation

can also lead to uneven participation, with some educators dominating discussions while others remain passive observers (Ekin, 2010). The participants opened up that factors like inadequacy and inefficiency of facilitators affect the quality of LAC sessions. Moreover, they expressed that facilitators were unprepared when conducting LAC sessions which resulted to less quality output as well. On the other hand, as emphasized in the study of Jhimson (2019), empowering facilitators with the skills to structure discussions, manage group dynamics, and extract actionable strategies from conversations can significantly enhance the overall experience for teachers en-

gagement of teachers to actively engage in the LAC sessions. Moreover, ensuring continuous LAC effectiveness requires ongoing evaluation and adaptation, which can be a demanding task amidst competing priorities. Despite these challenges, the potential benefits of LACs for teachers and learners are undeniable, and can be addressed through clear communication, dedicated resources, effective facilitation, and ongoing support (Eksi, 2010).

(2019) that the limited time allotted feels like a run, hindering in-depth discussions and comprehensive problem-solving. Also, time limitations can cause frustration and a sense of missed opportunities, leaving both teachers and the LAC's potential untapped (Ekin, 2010). Thus, unless schools prioritize allocating dedicated time and address scheduling conflicts, the vision of effective LACs might remain just a misconception (Jhimson, 2019). By addressing this challenge effectively, schools and educational institutions need to recognize and prioritize the value of LACs, consider flexible meeting times, and give ample support to teachers in overcoming the time-related constraints (Hismanoğlu, 2010).

can also lead to uneven participation, with some educators dominating discussions while others remain passive observers (Ekin, 2010). The participants opened up that factors like inadequacy and inefficiency of facilitators affect the quality of LAC sessions. Moreover, they expressed that facilitators were unprepared when conducting LAC sessions which resulted to less quality output as well. On the other hand, as emphasized in the study of Jhimson (2019), empowering facilitators with the skills to structure discussions, manage group dynamics, and extract actionable strategies from conversations can significantly enhance the overall experience for teachers en-

Fig. 4. Emerging themes on the challenges of teachers in engaging to Learning Action Cell

gaged in Learning Action Cells. Similarly, by addressing the challenge of inadequate facilitation, educators can maximize the benefits of collaborative learning and contribute more effectively to their professional growth and the improvement of teaching practices (Lavy,

2011).

To address this challenge, it is essential for schools and educational leaders to invest in facilitation training for those responsible for guiding LACs (Ryan, 2019).

3.2.3. Resource Limitations—The resource limitation challenges faced by teachers engaging in Learning Action Cells (LACs) present a substantial hurdle to the effectiveness of the implementation of the learning sessions. Resources, whether in the form of time, materials, or technological support, are crucial for the successful implementation of LAC initiatives. The resource limitation challenges faced by teachers engaging in Learning Action Cells (LACs) present a substantial hurdle to the effectiveness of the implementation of the learning sessions. Resources, whether in the form of

time, materials, or technological support, are crucial for the successful implementation of LAC initiatives. from educational institutions, ensuring teachers have the necessary support, time, and materials to fully participate in Learning Action Cells (Huang, 2007). By overcoming these challenges, educators can more effectively harness the benefits of collaborative learning and contribute to continuously improving their teaching practices (Lavy, 2011). Figure 4 shows the Challenges of Teachers in Engaging in Learning Action Cells and the emergence of the three themes: Time constraints, Inadequate facilitation, and Resource limitations

3.3. Educational Management Insights Drawn from the Findings of the Study—The study’s findings offer valuable insights for educational management, which can update strate-

gic decisions and foster a culture of continuous improvement. The challenges identified, such as time constraints and inadequate facilitation, highlight areas where targeted support and in-

terventions are needed. Educational management can leverage these insights to design and implement structures that address these challenges, ensuring that teachers have the necessary time, resources, and facilitation support to engage in collaborative professional development fully. Moreover, the study emphasizes the significance of aligning professional development efforts with broader school goals, em-

phasizing the need for coherence and integration within the school's strategic vision (Huang, 2007). By drawing upon these insights, school leaders can create a more responsive and effective system, ultimately contributing to the enhancement of teaching practices and learner outcomes within the institution (Kazmi et al., 2011).

*3.3.1. Cultivating collaborative culture—*The success of Learning Action Cells in improving teaching practices is intricately linked to establishing a culture that values collaboration, shared learning, and open communication among teachers. This insight prioritizes initiatives that raise a collaborative belief, allowing teachers to engage in meaningful discussions, share insights, and collectively address challenges. Emphasizing the importance of collaboration in professional development can influence school policies and practices, encouraging a more inclusive and supportive environment. By intentionally cultivating a collaborative culture, educational institutions can enhance the

effectiveness of Learning Action Cells and contribute to a broader positive transformation in the school's overall learning environment. As revealed by the participants, LAC promotes collaboration and curriculum improvement. Participants 4 and 7 also added that LAC creates a supportive environment and open communication that enhances teaching. According to Guzon et.al. (2023), a collaborative culture is essential for Learning Action Cells (LACs) success. Therefore, promoting a collaborative culture within LACs through group work, shared responsibilities, and mutual support can significantly enhance students' and educators' learning experiences and outcomes.

*3.3.2. Professional development integration—*An insightful finding from the study on teachers' engagement with Learning Action Cells highlights the huge implications of integrating professional development into teachers' existing experiences. The findings emphasize that teachers' engagement with Learning Action Cells, as collaborative platforms, serves as enablers for meaningful professional growth. This insight transmits substantial associations for educational management, suggesting that professional development should not be viewed as isolated events but rather woven into the daily practices and interactions of educators (Ryan, 2019). The participants' remarks captured professional development integration. They shared that LAC provides opportunities for teachers to

meet their individual needs and create a learning community. According to Kazmi et. al. (2011), by recognizing the value of continuous learning and collaboration, educational leaders can strategically integrate professional development initiatives, such as Learning Action Cells, into the regular routines of teachers. The study encourages a shift in mindset, urging educational management to view professional development as an ongoing, integral component of teachers' roles rather than a separate and occasional endeavor. By embracing this insight, institutions can foster a culture where educators are consistently engaged in collaborative learning, resulting in sustained professional growth and, ultimately, improved teaching practices (Ekin, 2010).

Fig. 5. Emerging Themes on the educational management insights drawn from the findings of the study

3.3.3. *Continuous improvement*—A salient insight drawn from the study on teachers’ engagement with Learning Action Cells is the vital importance of adopting a culture of continuous improvement within educational institutions. The findings highlight that the success of Learning Action Cells in enhancing teaching practices is deeply intertwined with continuous learning and refinement. This involves recognizing the achievements and encouraging an ongoing cycle of reflection, feedback, and adaptation in response to evolving educational needs. Through the perspective of continuous improvement, Learning Action Cells become not just an avenue for group effort but a driving force for the continuity of progress that will sustain quality in teaching and learning practices. The responses of Participants, who emphasized that

LAC offers opportunities for professional development and improvement, provided insight on continuous improvement. Teachers learned from each other and enhanced the teaching-learning process. Lavy (2011) highlighted that embracing the concept of continuous improvement can help educational institutions create structures that support regular self-assessment, collaborative problem-solving, and innovative teaching strategies. This insight urges a departure from static approaches to professional development, emphasizing the dynamic nature of teaching and the need for adaptive practices (Jhimson, 2019). Figure 5 shows the Educational management insights drawn from the findings of the study and the emergence of the three themes: Cultivating collaborative culture, Professional development integration, and Continuous improvement.

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this chapter, I present a summary of the study, drawing implications and future directions from the summary of the findings. The purpose of my study was to find out how teachers engage with Learning Action Cell, including how their interaction during Learning Action Cell sessions influenced their professional development experiences and the impact of teaching practices,

attitudes, and skills.

4.1. Findings—To achieve the research objectives, I used a qualitative phenomenological method with thematic analysis. In adherence to Cresswell's (2006) guidelines, open-ended questions for interviews were applied to get an authentic understanding of people's experiences. Furthermore, through the interview approach, I encouraged my teacher participants to fully and openly discuss their definition or meaning of the phenomenon being explored, which were the stories of their engagement with Learning Action Cells. Based on the results of the thematic analysis of the responses from

4.2. Implications—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. Teachers' engagement with Learning Action Cells (LACs) emphasized the transformative impact of collaborative professional development and nurtured teachers' problem-solving skills and innovative attitudes that led to increased learners' engagement during the teaching-learning process. Teachers consistently expressed a deep sense of professional growth by actively participating in reflective discussions, sharing effective teaching strategies, and receiving constructive feedback from their colleagues. The collective feature of Learning Action Cells promotes a supportive environment, enabling educators to address specific challenges in their classrooms and jointly explore innovative solutions. These experiences contributed to teachers' increased awareness of their teaching practices and a deeper understanding of their shared instructional teaching approaches. The challenges teachers encountered during their engagement in the Learning Action Cell enlighten the difficulties in collaborative learning. Teachers frequently deal with time constraints, juggling their participation in LACs

the participants of the study, the following findings and their corresponding themes were revealed: the experiences of teachers in engaging to Learning Action cell probed in promoting collaboration and shared learning, increasing learners' engagement and enhancing problem-solving and innovative skills. The challenges of teachers in engaging to Learning Action Cell employed were: time constraints, inadequate facilitation, and resource limitations. The educational management insights drawn from the study's findings were cultivating collaborative culture, professional development integration, and continuous improvement.

alongside numerous responsibilities. Thus, attendance and active involvement are persistent challenges, influenced by competing demands on educators' schedules. Maintaining a balance between structured discussions and actionable steps can also pose complications, with the varying levels of commitment among participants that could contribute to inconsistencies in engagement that require strategies to foster a shared dedication to the collaborative learning process. Moreover, sustaining Learning Action Cells over the long term and ensuring alignment with broader school goals emerge as daunting challenges. These findings highlighted the need for meticulous approaches and ongoing support structures to effectively address teachers' complex challenges during their participation in Learning Action Cells. The study's findings imply the importance of Learning Action Cells (LACs), which extend far beyond individual teachers' control and profoundly impact learners and the entire school community. As teachers refine their instructional methods through reflective discussions and peer feedback, the quality of their teaching improves, fostering a culture of excellence. This, in turn, has direct

implications for learners, wherein they benefit from teachers who are engaged in ongoing professional growth and deliver an enriched educational experience that is dynamic, innovative, and fitted to their diverse learning needs. Learning Action Cells contribute to cultivating a positive and supportive culture, which has academic implications and extends to the holis-

tic development of learners and the overall enhancement of the school's educational environment. Thus, Learning Action Cells became a foundation for sustainable growth, connecting teachers, learners, and the broader school community in a shared commitment to educational excellence.

4.3. Future Directions—Based on the study's findings, it was important that they are properly relayed and used by the significant people for whom this research was intended. The school principals or school heads may ensure that time constraints, commitment levels, and alignment with school goals are effectively addressed within the learning action cell sessions and advocate for sufficient resource allocation to optimize the effectiveness of LAC initiatives. Teachers may constantly be reflective and deeply understand the transformative impact of their engagement in collaborative learning. They may also uphold their continued support and expansion of LAC initiatives within their schools. Teachers may also take ownership of their professional development and contribute to a more passionate and effective educational community. The learners may actively participate in the teaching-learning pro-

cess to gain a more enriched and practical learning experience. They may be well aware of the importance of their holistic development and academic achievements and be proactive and eagerly participate in integrating teachers' innovative teaching practices. Other stakeholders may provide support for the appropriate implementation of Learning Action Cells. Stakeholders must sustain a collaborative relationship with school personnel, recognize their influence on teacher development and learners' achievement, and make an effort to support decisions and shape policies to invest in the success of the whole educational community. Future researchers may conduct the same study in a different location and with different participants. They may also explore other factors contributing to successful collaborative learning communities and investigate the long-term effects of Learning Action Cells on teaching practices, student outcomes, and school culture.

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